

RAiD

Research Activity Identifier

Partners working on this component

Component Overview

RAiD is a persistent identifier (PID) for research projects and activities that is now in production in Australia and Europe. Governed by ISO Standard 23527:2022 with the Australian Research Data Commons (ARDC) as the global Registration Authority, RAiD has been successfully implemented in the European context through FAIRCORE4EOSC, with SURF Netherlands serving as the European Registration Agency. The implementation across the European Open Science Cloud demonstrates RAiD's flexibility in different research contexts.

RAiD consists of a unique, resolvable DOI and a metadata record that connects organisations, people, inputs, and outputs to projects. It serves as a container for other PIDs (ORCID, ROR, DOI, etc.), linking research components while tracking project changes over time.

RAiD helps researchers by:

- Reducing administrative burden through automated metadata reuse
- Providing a single source of truth for project information
- Enabling multi-party administration across institutions
- Generating standardised landing pages for project discovery
- Supporting hierarchical relationships between projects
- Tracking project evolution through versioned metadata

RAiD contributes significantly to FAIRCORE4EOSC's PID Graph and RD Graph components, supplying crucial project metadata to Scientific Knowledge Graphs (SKGs). It implements DataCite DOI infrastructure and content negotiation standards, enhancing interoperability with other EOSC PID services.

The RAiD system enables funders to track research outputs and impacts, while research organisations benefit from improved project management and reporting capabilities, making research more transparent by exposing a project's make-up and evolution over time.

Functionalities

RAiD is a persistent identifier system for research projects, combining a unique DOI-based ID with structured metadata. It supports project management through a three-tiered schema (Core, Extended, Local) and allows users to:

- Mint RAiDs via web app or API
- Link projects to components using PIDs (ORCID, ROR, DOI, etc.)
- Track project evolution with versioning
- Assign access permissions for collaborative editing
- Resolve RAiDs to standardised landing pages
- Access metadata via API in multiple formats

RAiD is operated by Registration Agencies using RAiD Service Software, which includes a React-based web interface and a Java-based API. DOI minting is implemented via DataCite, with secure authentication from multiple identity providers. The metadata model is purpose-built for research projects.

The distributed architecture supports global adoption while ensuring centralised resolution through raid.org. Registration Agencies retain local control, including the ability to customise Extended metadata and define Local metadata fields, ensuring flexibility and global discoverability.

Impact

RAiD addresses a gap in the PID ecosystem, transforming research management across the entire research landscape.

For researchers, RAiD reduces administrative burden by reducing redundant data entry, improves project metadata accuracy, and supports research integrity through comprehensive tracking of project evolution. Research organisations benefit from enhanced reporting, improved collaboration, and strategic intelligence about research activities.

Funders can see the outcomes and impacts of their investments, with tracking extending beyond usual grant reporting in time and scope.

By connecting diverse research components through the PID Graph, RAiD enables comprehensive analysis of the research ecosystem, informing evidence-based policy development.

As adoption grows globally, RAiD will establish a universal language for describing research projects, fostering international collaboration and enabling more sophisticated research assessment.

Discover the RAiD Service